

D.5.1 – Identification of criteria for the selection of a model pathway

WP5 – Development of credible pathways for equitable, just, and fair energy transitions

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<i>Abstract</i>	<p>This report aims to identify and apply criteria for a 'model' pathway to be used later in the project for the co-creation of pathways that integrate considerations of gender into the design of socio-technical systems aimed at energy transition. The report is based on the earlier project work, mainly the review of literature at the nexus of energy and gender, and the collection of new data in WP1-3 to select criteria for defining the pathways. In the earlier gEneSys work, key theoretical frameworks were reviewed and assessed by applying the Gendered Innovation Approach (GIA) to select key topics, criteria (and indicators) that will be used for the model pathway. The analysis of pathways, including the dominant Net Zero pathway, demonstrates that gender and other social inequality criteria and indicators should be included in developing model pathways to help ensure just and fair energy transition processes and outcomes. A description of the methodology and process for this model pathway is described, considering credible scenarios for the implementation of the pathways. The explanation of how these models will be analysed in the following stage of the gEneSys work with key energy transition stakeholders, using backcasting methodology, is presented at the end of the report.</p>

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ACRONYMS

AI	Artificial intelligence
BFO	foundational ontology
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CCUS	Carbon Capture Utilisation and storage
DER	Decentralization and Distributed Energy Resources
ERA	European Research
Energy-SHIFTS	Energy Social Science and Humanities Innovation Forum Targeting
ESMAP	Energy Sector Management Assistance Programme
ESO	Energy System Ontology
GEA	Global Energy Assessment
GIA	Gendered Innovation Approach
GBEP	Global Bioenergy Partnership
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
JRC	Joint Research Center
LGBTQIA+	Lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, queer or questioning, intersex, asexual, and more
PV	Photovoltaic
SET-Plan	Strategic Energy Technology Plan
STEM	Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics
UN	United Nations
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organization
WRI	World Resources Institute

1. Introduction

The gEneSys project's aims are to advance understanding of gender dimensions in energy research, innovation, and socio-economic development to help accelerate the progress to energy transition and create more gender equitable, just, and sustainable outcomes (gEneSys, 2024). gEneSys conceptualises energy transition as a dynamic, gendered, mission-oriented socio-technical innovation ecosystem with technological, social, environmental, governance, and economic subsystems, each with its own sustainability visions, implementation concerns, power relations, values and priorities, as well as change actors and stakeholders, yet linked so that events and changes in individual subsystem may also influence developments in other subsystems (Pollitzer, 2023). One of the activities of the project (WP5) centres on the development of credible energy transition pathways that can deliver equitable and just outcomes.

Several theories and conceptual frameworks have been proposed to support development of a socially just energy transition by exploring the intersections between energy systems, social equity, and sustainability concerns. They include socio-technical transitions theory, environmental justice theory and intersectionality theory, among others. Globally, the Net Zero ambition has been stated as the core goal of the drive to reduce Greenhouse Gases (GHG) emission. In order to achieve this goal, different mitigation measures have been proposed and some are being implemented including the idea of the transition from traditional energy sources and systems to the more sustainable and fair alternatives. Addressing social justice within energy transition pathways involves ensuring equitable access to affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy resources for all communities, regardless of their socioeconomic status, geographic location, or demographic characteristics.

This report presents a review of the theories deployed to support energy transition. The analysis builds on the results of other research activities conducted within the gEneSys project, specifically D1.1 "Systematic literature review of studies at the nexus of gender equality and sustainable energy systems and ontology of energy systems", and additional analytical reviews of the literature at the nexus of gender and energy. Theories explaining energy transition issues have a strong link to the policy goals of the United Nations agenda on Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and its Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC, 2024).

In the analysis presented in this document, we propose a set of criteria for the development of a 'model' energy transition pathway that can then be used as a tool to gather context-relevant input from appropriate stakeholders to co-develop 'credible' pathways to gender-socially equal, just, and fair transition outcomes. The co-creation is an iterative process where the criteria and pathways can produce feedback effects (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Methodological process

The report is divided in the six sections: 1. Synthesis of gEneSys-produced research (D1.1 and D1.2); 2. Overview of the role of gender in the interpretations of Net Zero and just transitions; 3. Gender-related assumptions in existing theoretical frameworks for achieving just energy transition; 4. Proposal for a framework of criteria for energy transition pathways; 5. Proposal for criteria for a model pathway; 6. Proposal for a methodology for engagement of stakeholders in co-creation activities.

2. Synthesis of gEneSys research

This section summarises the research conducted by the gEneSys team during the first half of the project, which focused on understanding interactions between gender and energy, which cover energy policies, access, and usage and potentially different impacts on men and women due to their different societal roles, responsibilities, and power structures (UNWomen and UNIDO, 2023). ESMAP (2018) acknowledged that the conversation around gender and energy is evolving from viewing women as part of vulnerable groups to recognizing them as crucial change agents in roles such as consumers, producers, distributors, and decision-makers throughout the energy sector. gEneSys also recognises the important contribution roles that women can make to achieving energy transition as researchers, innovators, and entrepreneurs.

The gEneSys project has made several contributions to the research on energy transition. The first one is the Energy System Ontology (ESO) ([D1.1](#)), which provides a comprehensive conceptual view of the energy system based on the analysis of existing ontologies found in the scientific literature. Unlike other energy ontologies which focus mainly on technical aspects (e.g. OEO and SAREF4ENER), ESO includes concepts from various subsystems, described below and shown in Figure 2:

1. Environmental subsystem, which addresses CO₂ emissions, environmental protection, ecosystem risks, with emphasis on global warming, mitigation strategies, resilience, and climate change.
2. Strategy subsystem, which recognizes the influence of environmental concerns on energy strategies, as well as political dimensions such as energy security, international cooperation, and agreements.
3. The policy subsystem, which considers policy making, frameworks, implementation, acceptance, and governance involvement, including considerations of social justice.
4. The behavioural subsystem, which focuses on energy consumption, demand, markets, and individual, household, and organizational behaviour.
5. Operational subsystem, which explores technological and organizational aspects of energy, including general and specific energy system concepts.

Details of how the ESO relates to other ontologies and concepts can be found also in [D1.2](#) (page 6-13).

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Figure 2. Conceptual framework for building the Energy System Ontology (D1.1 page13)

The second gEneSys contribution to the research on energy transition is the systematic literature review (SLR) of research at the nexus of energy and gender. SLR identified 400 relevant publications with 288 in scientific journals and 138 in the grey literature. The dominant topics covered were: 1. Transition to modern energy; 2. Employment/work; 3. Knowledge/awareness; 4. Perception; 5. Attitudes/behaviour; 6. Health; 7. Empowerment. The overall conclusion is that most technology reports fail to consider gender and that only a minority of studies translate finding into evidence for policy.

gEneSys researchers have also applied a gender lens to the assessment of the energy systems knowledge communities (D1.2) looking in particular at the gender composition in the environment, strategy, operation, behaviour and policy domains. The results show a pronounced overall gender divide, with males dominating most knowledge-producing subcommunities. A significant involvement of women has been identified in the environment subsystem, but the largest dominance of men has been observed in the operation and strategy subsystems. These results suggest a need for further analysis to see if the dominance of men in energy knowledge production contributes to the gaps on gender knowledge observed in the systematic literature review.

gEneSys researchers have also analysed the National Recovery and Resilience Plans and concluded that these policies lack gender perspectives, neglecting women's needs and roles, and when gender is considered, its influence is only partially identified.

Overall, the results from the four gEneSys studies conducted so far suggest 1) urgent need for more concerted efforts to integrate considerations of gender in research on energy transition and 2) the necessity to close gender gaps in the policies on energy transition, which act as obstacles to fair and just outcomes.

3. Overview of the role of gender in the interpretations of Net Zero and just transitions

One of the tasks of the gEneSys project is to identify "credible" pathways to fair and just energy transition, which necessitate consideration of gender equality as a driver and benefit of the chosen

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interventions and expected outcomes. **Net zero** is a technical concept that refers to the balance between the amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions produced and the amount removed from the atmosphere. Achieving net zero means that any emissions are balanced by absorbing an equivalent amount from the atmosphere, which is essential to limit global warming and mitigate climate change impacts (UN, 2024). <https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/net-zero-coalition>. It is important to note that the net-zero scenario is only *a* pathway, rather than *the* pathway, to achieving net-zero CO₂ emissions in the energy sector by 2050 (IEA, 2021; WRI, 2021; 2024).

Net Zero sets a limit on global warming to 1.5°C and recognizes different strategies to achieve it, such as:

1. Emissions Reduction:
 - Decarbonizing Energy: Shifting from fossil fuels to renewable energy sources like solar, wind, and hydropower.
 - Energy Efficiency: Improving energy efficiency in buildings, transportation, and industries.
2. Carbon Removal:
 - Techniques to remove CO₂ from the atmosphere, including afforestation and reforestation, soil carbon sequestration, and direct air capture technologies.
3. Carbon Offsetting:
 - Compensating for emissions by funding projects that reduce or remove GHGs.
4. Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS): Technologies that capture CO₂ emissions from sources like power plants and store it underground.
5. Behavioural Changes: Encouraging sustainable lifestyles, such as reducing meat consumption and increasing public transportation use.

Achieving Net Zero may be one of the most difficult challenges facing societies. The International Energy Agency (IEA, 2021) and IRENA (2024) have included in their roadmaps different technologies and scenarios to support the energy transition through electrification and efficiency as key drivers of change, backed by renewables, hydrogen and sustainable biomass. The IPCC (2018) analysed 90 individual scenarios that have at least a 50% chance of limiting warming in 2100 to 1.5 °C (IPCC, 2018). Only 18 of these scenarios have net-zero CO₂ energy sector and industrial process emissions by 2050. That means that only one-in-five of the 1.5 °C scenarios assessed by the IPCC have the same level of emissions reduction.

Little is discussed about other possible pathways to consider along Net Zero. Although the road map of the IEA (2021) recognises that the transition to net zero is for and about people and requires the involvement of citizens, it fails to consider the effects of existing gender inequalities or the opportunities to create gender equality benefits.

The Agency (2021) considers the involvement of all citizens and particularly through behavioural changes (as also analysed in the Ontology). These are linked to consumer choices (e.g. use of energy efficient technologies), and to behavioural changes, more obvious in advanced (e.g. use of bikes, reducing flights, etc) (Figure 3). But this also has relevance in the Global South, providing access to electricity and clean cooking

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Figure 3. Impact of behaviour changes on final energy consumption. Source: IEA (2021)

In order to move away from fossil fuels to achieve the energy transition, trade-offs have been considered particularly on jobs loss from the fossil fuel industry and jobs created in energy transitions in the IEA scenarios towards Net Zero (IEA, 2022).

The power sector is estimated to be the main job provider for the transition but shortages of skilled labour in clean energy construction projects (currently seen) show the importance of strategic and proactive labour policies to build the workforce needed for the rapid expansion of clean energy technologies (IEA, 2022, page 177). These analyses remain gender blind with no further assessment of the implications and opportunities by gender. It is important to note that the IEA's net-zero scenario is only *a* pathway, rather than *the* pathway, to achieving net-zero CO₂ emissions in the energy sector by 2050 (IEA, 2021; WRI, 2021).

In order to move towards a Net Zero pathway, it is necessary to consider a just transition. This aims to ensure that the shift to a low-carbon economy is fair and inclusive, minimizing the negative social and economic impacts on workers and communities. Some organisations have focused their work on principles for just transitions. They tend to be oriented towards climate change rather than for energy pathways. Nevertheless, some of these principles can also be applied towards a just energy transition. For instance, the World Resources Institute has a programme oriented to drive equitable Green Development through Just Transition. The Just Transition Work Programme (JTWP) (WRI, 2024) that considers five principles which are centred on topics such as social equity and stakeholder engagement (Ensuring People-centred Climate Action and Addressing Global Inequity and Rejecting Oppressive Global Systems); Channelling Unconditional Support from Developed Countries; Creating Comprehensive and Flexible Just Transition Pathways; Building Synergies with Other Global Climate-related Workstreams. Some of these topics are also related to new forms of skilled jobs and economic diversification that may ensure social protection.

Achieving net zero and ensuring a just transition are critical components of global climate action. While the path to net zero involves significant technological, economic, and social changes, ensuring that this transition is just and equitable is paramount to its success. Key efforts related to policy integration, financial support and international cooperation will be key for its achievement. It requires coordinated efforts across all levels of society, from international organizations to local communities, and robust policy frameworks that prioritize both environmental sustainability and social justice.

The International Energy Agency Roadmap for the Global Energy Sector (IEA, 2021) has outlined comprehensive strategies and policies to achieve net zero emissions by 2050, ensuring that this transition is both inclusive and fair. Central to this transition is the concept of a "just transition," ensuring that the shift to a low-carbon economy is equitable and benefits all stakeholders, particularly

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those who might be adversely affected. Here are the key components of the IEA's net zero and just transition framework:

Pathway to Net Zero through an energy sector transformation:

- Energy Efficiency: Significant improvements in energy efficiency across all sectors.
- Renewable Energy: Rapid deployment of renewable energy sources like solar and wind.
- Electrification: Increased electrification of end-use sectors (e.g., electric vehicles, heat pumps).
- Hydrogen and Bioenergy: Expanded use of low-carbon hydrogen and sustainable bioenergy.
- Carbon Capture: Deployment of carbon capture, utilization, and storage (CCUS) technologies.
- Innovation: Accelerated development and deployment of emerging technologies.

The roadmap emphasizes the need for significant investment in clean energy technologies and infrastructure, estimated at around \$5 trillion annually by 2030. It also outlines essential policy measures, including carbon pricing, subsidies for clean energy, and regulations to phase out fossil fuels. Finally, it encourages research and development in new technologies to support the transition. The only mentions of social approaches are that “Energy transitions have to take account of the social and economic impacts on individuals and communities, and treat people as active participants” (IEA, 2021, page 11). While the roadmap provides a comprehensive strategy, its implementation faces several challenges. However, there are no mentions of just transition or gender focus.

Several pathways exist for energy transitions, each with its unique combination of **technologies, policies, and societal changes**. These pathways aim to shift energy systems away from fossil fuels towards cleaner, more sustainable alternatives while addressing social, economic, and environmental challenges. Some examples are presented below:

1. Renewable Energy Deployment:
 - This pathway involves scaling up the deployment of renewable energy technologies such as solar, wind, hydroelectric, and geothermal power. Key strategies include incentivizing renewable energy investment, improving grid integration, and supporting research and development to reduce costs and improve efficiency.
2. Energy Efficiency and Conservation:
 - Energy efficiency and conservation pathways focus on reducing energy consumption through improvements in technology, building design, transportation systems, and industrial processes.
3. Decentralization and Distributed Energy Resources (DERs):
 - Decentralization pathways aim to shift energy generation and consumption away from centralized power plants towards.
4. Electrification of Transportation and Heating:
 - Electrification pathways involve transitioning transportation and heating systems from fossil fuels to electricity, powered by renewable energy sources
5. Hydrogen Economy:
 - The hydrogen economy pathway involves the production, storage, and use of hydrogen as a clean energy carrier for various applications.
6. Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS):
 - CCUS technologies can help reduce emissions from existing fossil fuel infrastructure while supporting the transition to low-carbon energy sources.
7. Circular Economy and Resource Efficiency:
 - Strategies include recycling materials, recovering waste heat, and designing products and processes for longevity and reuse, thereby reducing the environmental footprint of energy systems.
8. Social Justice and Equity:

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- Social justice pathways prioritize equitable access to clean, affordable energy services for all communities, particularly marginalized and underserved populations. Strategies include targeted energy assistance programs, community-led renewable energy projects, and inclusive decision-making

These pathways are not mutually exclusive and can be combined and adapted to specific regional contexts, policy goals, and technological advancements.

3. Gender-related assumptions in existing theoretical frameworks for achieving just energy transition

Several theoretical and conceptual frameworks have been proposed in the literature to support the goal of achieving a just energy transition. Selected examples are summarised in Table 1. They have been selected because they offer potential (highlighted in bold) criteria for building the gEneSys the 'model' pathway.

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Table 1. Selected theories and frameworks related to gender (and social) justice in energy transitions

Sociotechnical transitions	Social Practice Theory (SPT)	Domestication theory	Social justice	The Social Construction of Technology	Sociotechnical imaginaries	Environmental Justice Theory	Energy Justice Framework	Inter-sectionality Theory	Feminist Political Ecology
<p>It refers to fundamental and systemic shifts in both societal and technological aspects that lead to significant changes in how societies function. These transitions often involve the interplay between social, economic, cultural, and technological dimensions, leading to new ways of organizing, producing, and consuming.</p>	<p>It is an interdisciplinary framework used to understand the social dynamics and routines that shape human behaviour. It provides a way of looking at social phenomena by focusing on the practices in which individuals and communities engage. These practices can include everyday activities that contribute to the reproduction and transformation of societal structures.</p>	<p>It is a framework used to analyse the adoption and integration of new communication technologies within everyday domestic life. This theory emerged in the context of studying the impact of technologies like television and later expanded to include other media and information and communication technologies (ICTs).</p>	<p>It involves within energy pathways ensuring equitable access to affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy resources for all communities, regardless of socioeconomic status, geographic location, or demographic characteristics.</p>	<p>SCOT explores how technologies are not just neutral objects with inherent properties but are socially shaped and constructed through a process involving various social actors, interests, and contexts.</p>	<p>It refers to collectively held, shared visions and narratives about the desirable relationships between society and technology. Sociotechnical imaginaries encompass not only specific technologies but also the broader social, cultural, political, and ethical frameworks in which these technologies are embedded.</p>	<p>It highlights the disproportionate burden of environmental pollution and hazards borne by marginalized communities, often due to factors such as race, income, and geographic location. Emphasizes the importance of addressing social inequalities in the distribution of environmental benefits and burdens, including access to clean energy and protection from the impacts of fossil fuel extraction and combustion.</p>	<p>It integrates concepts from environmental justice, social justice, and energy policy to analyse and address inequalities in energy systems. Considers issues such as energy poverty, energy affordability, energy access, and the distribution of energy benefits and risks across different social groups. Considers equitable energy governance, participatory decision-making processes, and community empowerment</p>	<p>It explores how social identities, such as race, class, gender, and sexuality, intersect and interact to shape individuals' experiences of privilege and oppression. In the context of energy transitions, highlights the importance of considering multiple dimensions of inequality.</p>	<p>This framework examines how gender, environment, and politics intersect, emphasizing the role of power relations and social justice in environmental issues. It critiques the traditional male-dominated narratives in environmental policy and decision-making.</p>

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4. Proposal for a framework of criteria for energy transition pathways

During the last thirty years indicators have gained more importance, being used to assess sustainability performance of different activities through the implementation of standards (Diaz-Chavez, 2014).

The four pillars of sustainability relevant to energy transition (Diaz-Chavez, 2014; 2015) are environmental, economic, social and governance. Woods and Diaz-Chavez (2007) defined conditions for monitoring bioenergy production:

- **principles:** defined as 'general tenets of sustainable production
- **criteria:** the conditions needed to achieve these tenets, and which help to define the indicators to be answered
- **indicators:** the individual questions that demonstrate how a producer meets a particular criterion

At a minimum, some of the characteristics shown in Table 2 should be considered to select indicators for assessing gender equality related 'credibility' of energy transition pathways.

Table 2. Characteristics of indicators (Sources: Januzzi, 2001; Cecchini, 2005; Diaz-Chavez 2014)

Characteristics	Description
Reliability and quality	The accuracy of the data; a measure of the information collected. Based on theory and science when possible.
Validity	Whether the indicator truly measures what it is supposed to measure
Realistic and practical	The collection of the data or information should be accurate and easily collectable, assuming the costs of collection.
Spatial and temporality	Consider temporal and spatial scale as well as changes over time
Simplicity and clarity	Clarity in design and simple in format; understandable for any person
Comparability	To allow comparisons at the adequate level
Consensus	Among different actors (local, national, international, sound groups)
Measurability	According to the data they are interpreting (qualitative/quantitative)
Reviewed	Considerations to update the information
Limitation and balance	In number. Extensive sets of indicators are not in use anymore. They should be short in number and balanced in the three dimensions of SD.
Links	To show causal links among indicators or relevant data (even processes) and to strengthen links among institutions.
Relevance	Direct relevance to the goal or objectives of the set of indicators

Traditional social indicators (and index) include demographics (age, sex, life expectancy, etc); education and culture (illiteracy, average schooling, etc); employment (unemployment rate; income, etc); income and poverty (GDP, GINI, etc); quality of life (satisfaction with house, infrastructure, etc); environment (air quality; water quality; water availability, etc); development (human development index; etc), among others.

In the European Union, gender indicators (sometimes referred to as statistical indicators) have been defined as the measure(s) upon which data is collected. These indicators have been devised to show gender gaps in access to resources and opportunities in areas such as education, employment, decision making and gender-based violence. Indicators can be used to show relative positions or positive or negative change (EIGE, 2019).

5. Proposed criteria for the gEneSys model pathway of energy transition

Energy transition pathways may be considered as normative descriptions of how the world could look like over time when realising a common goal, which is moving away from fossil fuels and address social issues such as just transitions while transitioning (Lieu et al., 2020). A transition is ... “a path towards environmentally sustainable and inclusive economies and societies, which promote and defend a set of shared values” (TPI, 2021, page 36). Ashfari et al. (2022) consider that implementing sustainability principles in the energy sector is a priority. Moving away from a fossil fuels as primary sources for energy towards renewable energy sources is a challenging process, because some technologies are still expensive, and the supporting infrastructure is still underdeveloped. The role of Governments on this transition is vital but it will be inefficient without community and institutional awareness of social in the energy sector (Ashfari et al., 2022).

Application of criteria and indicators can be found in different frameworks. For instance, criteria and indicators per type of energy (GBEP, 2011; Diaz-Chavez, 2014; 2015; IRENA, 2019, 2020, 2022); sustainability (Bell and Morse, 2003; Dahl, 2012); energy justice and transitions (Lieu et al., 2020; EC, 2021; Apergi et al., 2024; Murauskaite-Bull, 2024); socio-technical analysis in energy (Ashfari et al., 2022; van der Merwe, 2023); in statistics (EIGI, 2019; Energy Community, 2022; IRENA, 2024); energy poverty (Clancy et al., 2017); and those generated in AI (ChatGpt, 2024).

For the model pathway of energy transition, the proposed criteria are listed below in Figures 4 and 5. They are drawn from the research conducted by gEneSys and some additional consultation of the literature.

What do you consider a sustainable pathway in energy?

Which criteria would you include for a credible energy transition pathway? You can include up to three

Figure 4. Results of the rapid consultation of gEneSys consortium members using slido (Berlin, October 14, 2023).

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Figure 5. Elements of energy transition pathways and frameworks

From the theoretical frameworks described in Section 3, three theories can be clearly linked to energy transition pathways: social justice and intersectionality. Other theoretical frameworks have common points on criteria with these two and therefore show synergies (e.g. socio-technological diversity). Tables 3-5 below provide summaries of the theories with potential criteria and indicators to be considered when developing the model pathway and Table 6 shows selected topics and criteria for the model pathway.

Table 3. Summary of Socio-Technical Transitions Theory topics and criteria

Topic	Criteria
Technological Diversity	Variety of renewable energy technologies deployed (e.g., solar PV, wind, hydro, geothermal).
Institutional Innovation	Existence of policies and governance structures supporting renewable energy deployment.
Social Acceptance	Public attitudes and perceptions towards renewable energy projects
Equity and Justice	Distributional impacts of energy transition policies and projects
Resilience and Adaptability	Ability of the energy system to withstand and recover from disruptions

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Table 4. Summary of Intersectionality theory topics and criteria

Topic	Criteria
Multiple Social Identities	Intersectional analysis of energy access and impacts
Power Dynamics	Representation and participation of marginalized groups in decision-making processes.
Differential Impacts	Disproportionate impacts of energy policies and projects on marginalized communities.
Cultural Relevance	Recognition and incorporation of cultural values and knowledge into energy planning and decision-making

Table 5. Summary of Social justice theoretical framework topics and criteria

Topic	Criteria
Equitable Access:	Socially just energy pathways prioritize equitable access to energy services, including electricity, heating, cooling, and transportation fuels. This means ensuring that marginalized communities, such as low-income households and rural areas, have the same opportunities to access clean and affordable energy as more affluent or urban populations.
2. Affordability	Energy costs to be addressed by implementing policies and programs that make energy services more affordable for vulnerable populations (e.g. income-based energy assistance programs, energy efficiency measures, and targeted subsidies for renewable energy technologies).
3. Community Engagement and Empowerment	Socially just energy pathways prioritize community involvement, empowerment, and ownership of energy projects (e.g. community-led renewable energy initiatives, participatory planning processes, and partnerships between local governments, community organizations, and energy stakeholders).
4. Environmental Justice	Mitigating disparities by prioritizing clean energy technologies and siting energy infrastructure in a manner that minimizes environmental and health risks for frontline communities.
5. Job Creation and Economic Development	Investing in renewable energy deployment, energy efficiency retrofits, and sustainable infrastructure projects can create opportunities for local employment, workforce training, and small business development, helping to build more resilient and inclusive economies.
6. Equity in Energy Transition	Mitigate these challenges and ensure a fair and equitable transition for all (e.g. just transition policies, worker retraining programs, and support for impacted communities).
7. Cultural Relevance and Indigenous Rights	Respect Indigenous rights, sovereignty, and self-determination, recognizing the importance of Indigenous knowledge and traditional practices in shaping sustainable energy solutions (e.g. collaborative partnerships with Indigenous communities and meaningful consultation).

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Table 6 Selected topics, criteria and indicators for gender and energy pathways.

TOPIC	CRITERIA	INDICATORS
Employment and Economic Participation	1. Women's Employment in Energy Sectors	Number and percentage of women employed in renewable energy sectors (solar, wind, bioenergy, etc.).
		Comparison with men's employment in the same sectors.
	2. Gender Wage Gap:	Wage disparities between men and women in the energy sector.
		Average income of women compared to men in similar roles
	3. Leadership and Decision-Making Roles:	Proportion of women in senior, managerial, and decision-making positions within energy companies
		Representation of women on boards of energy companies and in government energy departments
	4. Access to Finance and Entrepreneurship:	Access to financial resources and support for women entrepreneurs in energy.
		Number of women-led businesses in the renewable energy sector
Energy Access and Equity	1. Household Energy Access	Differences in energy access between male- and female-headed households.
		Proportion of households using clean energy solutions, disaggregated by gender.
	2. Energy Decision-Making:	Women's participation in household and community decision-making regarding energy usage and investments
		Influence of women in the adoption of renewable energy technologies.
	3. Time and Labor Savings:	Impact of energy access on the time women spend on household chores (e.g., cooking, water collection).

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		Reduction in drudgery and physical labor due to improved energy access.
Health and Well-being	1. Health Outcomes:	Gender-specific health improvements due to cleaner energy sources (e.g., reduction in respiratory diseases from indoor air pollution).
		Access to healthcare facilities powered by renewable energy.
	2. Exposure to Indoor Air Pollution	Changes in indoor air quality due to adoption of clean cooking solutions.
		Health benefits for women and children from reduced exposure to smoke from traditional biomass.
Education and Skills Development	1. Access to Education and Training:	Enrollment rates of women in education and training programs related to renewable energy.
		Participation of women in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) fields relevant to energy.
	2. Skill Development Programs	Availability and accessibility of skill development programs for women in the energy sector.
		Outcomes of training programs, including job placements and career advancement for women.
Policy and Governance	1. Gender-Sensitive Policies:	Inclusion of gender perspectives in national and local energy policies.
		Existence and effectiveness of policies promoting gender equity in the energy sector.
	2. Representation in Policy-Making	Number of women involved in energy policy-making bodies and processes.
		Influence of women's voices in shaping energy policies and regulations.
Social Norms and Cultural Barriers	1. Cultural Attitudes	Societal attitudes towards women's roles in the energy sector.
		Perception of women working in traditionally

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		male-dominated energy industries.
	2. Barriers to Participation	Identification of cultural and social barriers limiting women's involvement in energy transitions.
		Efforts to address and reduce these barriers.
Community Impact and Benefits Distribution	1. Distribution of Benefits	Analysis of how benefits from energy projects are distributed among men and women.
		Equity in access to resources, training, and economic opportunities generated by energy projects
	2. Support Systems	Availability of support systems for women, such as childcare and flexible working conditions in the energy sector.
		Initiatives to create a conducive environment for women's participation in energy projects.

Table 6 of selected indicators will be discussed with stakeholders as indicated in section 6.

6. Proposal for a methodology for the engagement of stakeholders in co-creation of the model pathway.

To satisfy the conditions of credibility, gEneSys will engage relevant stakeholders in co-creation activities of the model pathway. Three scenarios are envisaged:

- Business as usual (BAU): where even with current international agreements in place, with a high carbon energy production and consumption.
- Green: Where low carbon innovations within energy systems focus on technological, institutional and physical infrastructure
- Climate justice and gender considerations within a social justice and intersectionality issues for low carbon innovation systems. This looks, not just at the technical but also social and gender issues.

The scenarios will be discussed with stakeholders where the selected topics and criteria will be applied (Figure 6).

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Figure 6. Proposed scenarios for pathway development

The prioritisation and application of criteria and indicators will follow the conceptual scheme as shown in Figures 7-8 (Clancey 2017, Trinomics, 2016; JRC, 2024)

Legend: ***(text bold and italics)*** indicates gender as a factor

Figure 7. Example of gender indicators operating in the drivers, causes and effects of energy poverty (Source Clancey et al., 2017, in JRC, 2024).

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Figure 8. Conceptual map of the drivers, causes and effects of energy poverty in the EU (Trinomics, 2016).

The selection process will follow Figure 9. From the selected topic criteria (single or multiple) or subsystem will be discussed to be included as part of the pathway. The figure shows a linear model, but it may be taking a different form such as in systems analysis where multi criteria can be included to analyse their relationships.

Figure 9. Model pathway with selected criteria/subtopics

The model will be based in topics, criteria and indicators to be discussed and final selection in workshops with stakeholders, mostly policy-makers and researchers. Using the selected topics, criteria and indicators of Table 6 using socio-technical transitions , intersectionality and social justice

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theoretical frameworks, a schematic representation of the topic-criteria-indicator are presented in figures Figure 10 Figure 11 below.

Figure 10. Examples of topics, criteria and indicators for socio-technology theoretical framework.

Figure 11. Examples of topics, criteria and indicators for intersectionality theoretical framework.

These topics and criteria will be discussed in the workshops, linked to another task within the gEneSys project (T5.4) where we will **Co-create pathways** and analyse the scenarios (Figure 5) with a backcasting methodology (e.g. Bibri, 2018; Kishita et al., 2017). This task will entail working closely with key stakeholders for the co-creation of credible and sustainable pathways that transform gender power relations and enable a fair and just energy transition.

7. Conclusions

In order to gain societal support for the move towards a Net Zero pathway, it is necessary to demonstrate that the processes and outcomes will be just. Some actors have focused their work on establishing the principles of just transitions. These efforts tend to be motivated by climate change issues rather than 'credible' energy transition pathways. Several possible pathways exist for energy transitions, each with its unique combination of technologies, policies, and societal changes. Whatever pathways are followed they must include not only a social perspective that involves the principles of justice, fairness and equity but associated with these principles specific gender equality benefits. This report sets the conditions for establishing gender equality criteria in a “model” pathway for energy transition. Defining and validating the model pathway will be a joint effort based on research and involving different stakeholders.

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